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The Impact of Domestic Violence on the Children and Family Dynamics: A Social Work Aspect

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Gian Chand

Associate Professor
Department Of Social
Work
BPS Mahila
Vishwavidyalaya Khanpur
Kalan
Sonapat, Haryana, India

Narender Kumar

Research Scholar
Department Of Social
Work
Kurukshetra University
Kurukshetra, Haryana,
India

Abstract

Domestic violence is a deeply entrenched social issue with devastating impacts on both individual well-being and family dynamics. Particularly in northern Indian states such as Delhi and Haryana, rising incidents of domestic violence have become a major concern, posing a significant threat to children's psychological health and the overall stability of the household. This paper explores the impact of witnessing domestic violence; especially violence by fathers toward mothers; on children's mental and emotional development. Domestic violence is not only a gender-based human rights violation but also a pressing public health issue with far-reaching consequences, particularly for women and children. This research applied a mixed-methods approach, integrating qualitative and quantitative analyses within a descriptive research design, to investigate the impact of domestic violence on children and family dynamics in Haryana and the National Capital Region (NCR). Data is utilized by the author from various research papers, case studies, based on primary data and government reports from Haryana, Delhi, and India, focusing on domestic violence incidents and their effects. In this regards, this study the impact of domestic violence on children and women, with a focus on its impact on their psychological, emotional, behavioral, social, economical, educational, and health aspects. Study would explore the scope of social work interventions to help the victims. The study highlights the urgent need for region-specific strategies, increased counseling services, and broader societal awareness to break the intergenerational cycle of violence and promote holistic family well-being. Special emphasis is placed on the role of the social work profession in identifying, supporting, and intervening in such cases. It is explored that there are some alarming statistics from UNICEF, which suggest that around 275 million children worldwide are exposed to violence within the home, often at the hands of trusted family members. Further, it is explored that according to the World Health Organization, approximately 35.00 percent of women globally have experienced physical or sexual violence by an intimate partner. Author highlighted a gross prevalence of abuse, identifying major contributing factors such as; patriarchy, gender issues of the society, financial instability, alcoholism, illiteracy, extramarital affairs, and dowry-related pressures. The study is concluded by the author with the suggestion of an urgent need for expanded support services, effective rehabilitation and counseling centres nationwide and effective and proper application of social work as a profession, to address both the immediate and generational impacts of domestic violence on children and on family dynamics.

Keywords

Domestic Violence, Child Abuse, Preventive Measures, Family Relationships, Trauma, Constitutional Safeguards, Human Rights

Introduction

Domestic violence, as defined by the Domestic Violence Act of 2005 in India, refers to any act or pattern of behavior that threatens the health, safety, or well-being of women and children (both boys and girls under 18 years of age). It includes physical, sexual, emotional, and economic harm, resulting in humiliation and suffering. Despite the legal provisions under the Domestic Violence Act, which allow women to prosecute adult men responsible for such violence, the prevalence of domestic violence continues to be alarmingly high across India, with significant implications for victims, particularly children and families. Domestic violence is a multifaceted issue that is not only limited to physical

abuse but also includes psychological abuse, verbal aggression, sexual assault, and economic deprivation, all of which contribute to the suffering of women and children.

In regions like Haryana, Delhi, and the National Capital Region (NCR), domestic violence has reached critical levels, deeply impacting children and family dynamics. While violence against women has been widely documented, the effect of domestic violence on children is an equally pressing concern that requires more attention. According to the United Nations Population Fund, nearly two-thirds of married women in India are victims of domestic violence, with 70.00 percent of women aged 15-49 subjected to beating, rape, or forced sexual abuse. This widespread violence disproportionately affects women, but its toll on children, who often witness these violent acts, is equally devastating. Domestic violence against children is a significant concern, with children and adolescents in urban areas often facing hidden violence within their homes. In rural areas, the forms of domestic violence may be more visible, yet still deeply ingrained in the culture. In Haryana and NCR regions, these issues are compounded by a strong patriarchal culture and social structure, where women's roles are often confined to being obedient wives and caretakers. Economic dependency, social stigma, fear of judgment, and lack of family support prevent most women from speaking out or leaving abusive relationships. Furthermore, verbal and emotional violence; though often harder to quantify; is pervasive and deeply damaging. Women are frequently insulted for their appearance, accused of being disrespectful to their husbands or in-laws, or humiliated for not bearing a male child. Verbal abuse can also take the form of character assassination, name-calling, or derogatory remarks for not bringing dowry or being less educated. Domestic violence has profound and far-reaching effects on children and family dynamics. It not only causes immediate physical harm but also leads to long-term psychological issues, disrupts family relationships, and hampers educational progress. While the Indian Constitution and various laws provide safeguards for children, the implementation and enforcement of these protections remain crucial. There is a need for increased awareness, education, and support systems to address domestic violence effectively and protect the rights of children. Apart from this, it is also explored in various research works that Social workers play a crucial role with the well-being of children and families in addressing this challenge through prevention, crisis response, support, and advocacy in Haryana and the National Capital Region. Therefore, the present study is an attempt to explore the causes, factors affecting the impact of domestic violence on children and on family dynamics in Haryana and NCR areas.

Objective of study

1. To understand the extent and types of domestic violence affecting children in Haryana and NCR.
2. To analyze the impact of domestic violence on children and in family dynamics in Haryana and NCR.
3. To explore the scope of social worker interventions in supporting the victims and provide them relief from their problems.

Review of Literature

Biswal, M. (2024). Analyzed that domestic violence is a pervasive issue that not only affects the primary victims but also has significant secondary effects on children who witness the abuse. Research has largely focused on the direct impact of domestic violence on the primary victim, but recent studies have begun to explore how children, as secondary victims, are impacted. It is explored that domestic violence leads to cognitive, behavioral, and emotional disturbances in children, with long-term consequences. Author suggested the importance of addressing domestic violence from a broader, systemic perspective to break the cycle of abuse against children and the overall family.

Carolin, P. A., & Xavier, G. G. (2020). Highlighted that domestic violence is such intimate partner violence, which has become a global issue that takes various forms, including physical, emotional, sexual abuse, and threats. Author explored that according to the World Health Organization; approximately 35.00 percent of women worldwide have experienced physical or sexual intimate partner violence (WHO, 2020). Further examined that the children exposed to such violence in their homes are also at high risk of physical abuse, which can lead to significant long-term physical and mental health problems. Author explored that according to a study, a staggering 275 million children globally are exposed to domestic violence, with many experiencing direct victimization (UNICEF, 2020). Author concluded that paper with the recommendations that to addresses these serious global human rights issues, there is a requirement of a comprehensive understanding of family dynamics and cultural contexts and effective protecting safeguards for women and children.

Kadhim, N. S., & Shreef, N. S. (2024). Conducted a study and found that domestic violence is a destructive force that deeply impacts children's development, particularly in societies where violence is prevalent. It is explored that in Iraq, domestic violence has had severe consequences on children, with 23 children killed in 2020 alone due to family violence, and many others suffering serious injuries such as fractures and burns. Author highlighted that UNICEF condemns such violence and advocates for stronger protective

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measures for children. It is recommended by the author that ensuring a safe and violence-free environment is crucial for the healthy development of children and for safeguarding their rights to dignity and privacy.

Roy, M. D. (2015). Found that violence is a pervasive force in the lives of children, with significant long-term effects. It is highlighted that the impact of witnessing violence in the home has been widely studied; with research indicating that exposure to such trauma can lead to conditions like anxiety, depression, and aggression in children. It is concluded that these children often exhibit social difficulties, struggling to form healthy relationships later in life, therefore, understanding the nature of domestic violence and its harmful impact on young minds, it is crucial to plan and execute effective remedial interventions and support systems to help these children cope and heal.

Rationale of the Study

Domestic violence continues to be one of the most deeply rooted social problems in India, with profound and far-reaching consequences on families; especially on children. In regions like Haryana and the National Capital Region (NCR), where patriarchal norms remain dominant and social stigma around abuse is strong, domestic violence often goes unreported and unaddressed. This study is particularly relevant in highlighting the intergenerational impact of domestic violence, focusing on how children growing up in violent households are emotionally, psychologically, and socially affected in Haryana and the National Capital Region. Apart from this, this study is thus crucial in addressing an overlooked dimension of domestic violence; its hidden impact on children and family structures and aims to inform both policy and community-level interventions to foster safer, healthier environments for future generations and also explored the important role of social work in helping the victims.

Methodology This research applied a mixed-methods approach, integrating qualitative and quantitative analyses within a descriptive research design, to investigate the impact of domestic violence on children and family dynamics in Haryana and the National Capital Region (NCR). Data is utilized by the author from various research papers, case studies, based on primary data and government reports from Haryana, Delhi, and India, focusing on domestic violence incidents and their effects.

Findings

As mentioned above, this research applied a mixed-methods approach, integrating qualitative and quantitative analyses within a descriptive research design, to investigate the impact of domestic violence on children and family dynamics in Haryana and the National Capital Region (NCR). Data is utilized by the author from various research papers, case studies, based on primary data and government reports from Haryana, Delhi, and India, focusing on domestic violence incidents and their effects. Therefore, it is found that domestic violence in Haryana and the NCR region has far-reaching consequences, not only for the victims but also for children and family dynamics. The various forms of abuse; physical, sexual, and psychological; inflict lasting harm on children, affecting their physical health, emotional well-being, relationships, and education. The root causes of domestic violence are deeply entrenched in societal norms, where women are often seen as inferior to men and are expected to adhere to traditional roles of submission and servitude. These patriarchal values often drive violence, particularly in situations of dissatisfaction related to dowry, family disagreements, and perceived failures in domestic roles, such as child-rearing or maintaining the household. The main findings of this research on *The Impact of Domestic Violence on Children and Family Dynamics: A Social Work Aspect* reveal that domestic violence is a pervasive issue that deeply affects both individual and collective well-being within families. Children who are exposed to domestic violence often experience a range of adverse effects that impact their emotional, psychological, and behavioral development. These effects include anxiety, depression, low self-esteem, sleep disturbances, difficulty concentrating, and in some cases, aggressive or withdrawn behavior. Many children internalize the trauma, leading to long-term consequences such as difficulty forming healthy relationships or engaging in risky behaviors during adolescence. The research highlights that these impacts are not limited to children who are physically abused; witnessing violence can be equally damaging, especially when it occurs over a prolonged period. In terms of family dynamics, the findings show that domestic violence often leads to a breakdown of trust and communication, role confusion, emotional detachment, and a constant atmosphere of fear and unpredictability. Non-abusive caregivers may also struggle with their own trauma and mental health challenges, affecting their ability to provide emotional support and stability to their children.

From a social work perspective, the findings emphasize the critical need for early identification and intervention. Social workers are often frontline responders in domestic violence cases and must be equipped with the knowledge and skills to assess risk, ensure safety, and coordinate a comprehensive response. This includes connecting families to protective services, legal resources, mental health care, and community support networks. A trauma-informed and culturally responsive approach is essential, as every family experiences and responds to violence differently depending on their background, beliefs,

and social context. The research also points to the importance of collaboration among social workers, schools, healthcare providers, law enforcement, and community organizations in order to provide a consistent and effective support system. Moreover, the findings stress the value of preventative efforts such as education, public awareness campaigns, and policy advocacy to challenge the normalization of violence and promote healthy family relationships. In summary, the research underscores that domestic violence is not only a personal or private matter but a complex social issue that requires coordinated, informed, and compassionate intervention; particularly from social work professionals; to protect children, support healing, and restore family stability.

Domestic Violence in Haryana, Delhi, and NCR Areas

Within the confines of home; where safety and comfort should prevail; many women in Haryana, Delhi, and the NCR region experience a starkly different reality. Domestic violence in these areas is not only prevalent but often goes unnoticed and unreported, masked by societal norms and cultural expectations that justifies or trivializes abuse. While Indian law criminalizes domestic violence, societal silence and deep-rooted patriarchal beliefs make enforcement a major challenge. According to a study by the International Center for Research on Women (ICRW, 2002), nearly 45.00 percent of Indian women reported being slapped, kicked, or beaten by their husbands. Shockingly, 32.00 percent of men admitted to having committed acts of violence against their pregnant wives. These statistics become even more distressing when coupled with data indicating that every hour; a woman in India dies due to domestic violence.

Effects of Domestic Violence on Children and Family Dynamics

- Physical Effects on Children- Children who witness or are involved in domestic violence may suffer from physical injuries, either directly from the violence or indirectly while trying to intervene.
- Psychological Effects- The trauma of witnessing or experiencing domestic violence can lead to significant psychological issues in children. These may include depression, anxiety, low self-esteem, and behavioral problems.
- Impact on Family Relationships- Domestic violence disrupts the family structure, leading to strained relationships between family members.
- Educational Challenges- Children exposed to domestic violence often face difficulties in their academic performance.

Constitutional Safeguards for Children- The Constitution of India provides several protections to ensure the welfare and rights of children, which are explained as follows-

- Article 21A- Guarantees the right to free and compulsory education for children aged 6 to 14 years.
- Article 24- Prohibits the employment of children in factories, mines, or any hazardous employment until the age of 14 years.
- Article 39(e)- Ensures that children are not abused and are not forced by economic necessity to enter occupations unsuited to their age or strength.
- Article 39(f)- Provides that children are given opportunities and facilities to develop in a healthy manner and in conditions of freedom and dignity.
- Article 45- Mandates early childhood care and education for all children until they complete the age of six years.
- These constitutional provisions aim to safeguard children from exploitation and ensure their overall development. Apart from these, there is a legal framework addressing domestic violence. India has enacted several laws to combat domestic violence and protect victims, which are as follows-
- Protection of Women from Domestic Violence Act, 2005- This law provides a comprehensive definition of domestic violence, encompassing physical, sexual, emotional, and economic abuse.
- Section 498A of the Indian Penal Code- Criminalizes cruelty by a husband or his relatives towards a woman, including physical and mental harm.
- Juvenile Justice (Care and Protection of Children) Act, 2015- Provides for the care, protection, and rehabilitation of children in need, including those affected by domestic violence.
- These laws are designed to provide immediate relief and long-term protection to victims of domestic violence, ensuring their safety and well-being.
- Study explored that exposure to consistent conflict and aggression within the home not only disturbs a child's sense of security but also alters their developmental trajectory. In the context of Haryana and NCR; regions marked by a mix of rural traditions and urban transitions; children often lack access to proper psychological support, making them vulnerable to the long-term consequences of domestic violence. Moreover, domestic violence disrupts the family dynamic, often resulting in fractured relationships, lack of trust, and diminished parental authority. Women, frequently the primary caregivers, struggle to maintain emotional availability for their children while coping with abuse themselves. The ripple effect of such violence is

felt throughout the family unit, weakening social bonds and perpetuating cycles of silence and trauma.

Types of Domestic Violence and Their Impact on Children and Family Dynamics in Haryana and NCR

- **Physical Violence-** In Haryana and the NCR region, physical violence is prevalent, with studies indicating that a significant percentage of women experience such abuse. For instance, a study in Gurugram found that 33.4.0 percent of women reported experiencing physical violence.
- **Sexual Violence-** Sexual violence refers to any non-consensual sexual act, including forced intercourse, molestation, or coercion. In the context of domestic settings, this often involves intimate partners or family members.
- **Psychological Violence-** Psychological violence includes verbal abuse, threats, humiliation, and controlling behaviors that undermine an individual's sense of self-worth. In Haryana and NCR.

Impact on Children and Family Dynamics

- **Physical Effects on Children-** Children exposed to domestic violence may suffer from physical injuries, either from direct involvement or from the trauma of witnessing abuse. These injuries can range from minor bruises to more severe harm.
- **Psychological Effects-** The psychological impact on children is profound. Exposure to domestic violence can lead to anxiety, depression, post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD), and other emotional disturbances.
- **Relationship Effects-** Witnessing or experiencing domestic violence can alter a child's perception of relationships. They may develop trust issues; have difficulty forming healthy relationships, or replicate abusive behaviors in their own relationships.
- **Educational Impact-** Children in abusive households often face challenges in their education. The stress and trauma associated with domestic violence can lead to decreased concentration, poor academic performance, and increased absenteeism.

Role of Social Workers in Domestic Violence, Protecting Children and Family Dynamics in Haryana and NCR

Social workers play a crucial role with the well-being of children and families in addressing this challenge through prevention, crisis response, support, and advocacy in Haryana and the National Capital Region, which are explained as given below-

- **Community Education and Awareness-** Social workers conduct community outreach programmes in both rural and urban areas to raise awareness about domestic violence and its warning signs.
- **Empowerment Programmes-** Social workers target vulnerable populations such as; women in low-income households, persons with disabilities and survivors of previous trauma.
- **Collaboration with Other Professionals-** Social workers coordinate with law enforcement for protection and legal action, healthcare providers for physical and mental health care, legal professionals to assist with restraining orders, custody issues, and other legal rights.
- **Role in Crisis Intervention and Support-** When prevention is not enough and violence has occurred, social workers become critical first responders offering practical, legal, and emotional support to victims and their families.
- **Crisis Counseling and Emotional Support-** Domestic violence leaves deep psychological scars; including trauma, fear, confusion, guilt, and isolation.
- **Advocacy for Victims-** Social workers step in as advocates and help the victims in the ways such as; filing police complaints and accompanying victims to legal proceedings, applying for restraining or protection orders, ensuring access to medical and psychological care and supporting access to social welfare schemes, child protection services, and housing support.
- **Protecting and Supporting Children-** Social workers ensure children are protected physically and emotionally. They may involve child protection agencies if necessary. They offer counseling for children, especially when separation from a parent is involved.
- **Rebuilding and Rehabilitation-** Social workers assist survivors in rebuilding their lives by; providing long-term counseling, helping with job placement or vocational training.

It is summarized by the author that in Haryana and NCR, social work is an essential and instrumental in protection, support, and transformation for victims of domestic violence. Their role is not only to react to violence but also to change the social conditions and attitudes that allow it to continue.

Conclusion

Domestic violence in Haryana and the NCR region has far-reaching consequences, not only for the victims but also for children and family dynamics. The various forms of abuse; physical, sexual, and psychological; inflict lasting harm on children, affecting their physical health, emotional well-being, relationships, and education. Author further concluded the significant and multifaceted impact of domestic violence on children and family dynamics, emphasizing the urgent need for effective social work intervention. Children exposed to domestic violence suffer emotional, psychological, and behavioral consequences that can persist into adulthood, affecting their ability to form healthy relationships and lead stable lives. The family environment, once a place of safety, becomes marked by fear, instability, and emotional disconnection. This deterioration in family dynamics often leads to long-term trauma and dysfunction. From a social work perspective, addressing these challenges requires a holistic, trauma-informed approach that prioritizes the safety and emotional well-being of both children and non-abusive caregivers. Social workers must serve not only as crisis responders but also as long-term advocates, guiding families through recovery and connecting them to critical resources. The findings of this research also underline the importance of community awareness, preventative education, and policy development in addressing domestic violence at its roots. Ultimately, breaking the cycle of domestic violence demands coordinated efforts across sectors, with social workers playing a vital role in restoring family stability, fostering resilience in children, and advocating for systemic change that ensures lasting safety and support for affected families.

It is recommended by the author that addressing domestic violence requires a multi-faceted approach, including legal reforms, social awareness, and community support. The role of social work is very important in addressing the impact of domestic violence in Haryana and NCR region on children and family dynamics.

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